

System identification of the FiO_2 to SpO_2 relationship during mechanical ventilation

P. von Platen^{1*}, A. Hallmann¹, A. Pomprapa¹, S. Leonhardt¹, P.A. Pickerodt², M. Ruß², M. Taher², W. Braun³, L. Hinken³, R. Köbrich⁴, R.C.E. Francis², and M. Walter¹

¹ Medical Information Technology, RWTH Aachen University, Aachen, Germany

² Department of Anesthesiology and Operative Intensive Care Medicine, Charité-Universitätsmedizin Berlin, Berlin, Germany

³ Fritz Stephan GmbH, Gackenbach, Germany

⁴ EKV Elektronik GmbH, Leiningen, Germany

*Corresponding author, email: platen@hia.rwth-aachen.de

Abstract: For physiological closed-loop control of mechanical ventilation, the relationship between fraction of inspired oxygen and oxygen saturation is required. A system identification method is proposed which models this relationship as a non-linear Hammerstein model. The static non-linearity is modelled as a fourth order polynomial and the linear dynamics are modelled as a first order system with dead time. Results from data from one animal experiment show good accuracy of this model. This model could be used for controller testing or as a surrogate measurement in case of sensor failure.

© Copyright 2021

This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License CC-BY 4.0., which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

I. Introduction

Patients suffering from respiratory failure require a mechanical ventilator to ensure sufficient oxygen (O_2) is made available to the body and excess carbon dioxide (CO_2) is expelled from the body. A clinician is required to constantly adapt the ventilator settings to ensure the patient remains in a stable and safe target state. Using a closed-loop controller to replace the manual tuning of ventilation parameters would reduce the workload and stress of the clinicians managing the mechanical ventilator.

Various approaches for closed-loop control have been proposed, in which the oxygenation of the patient, measured using a pulse-oximeter (SpO_2), is regulated by adjusting the fraction of inspired oxygen (FiO_2) [1]. Modelling the dependency between FiO_2 and SpO_2 is therefore required for designing and testing these closed-loop controllers. The models can further be used for online prediction, simulation and (sensor) fault detection [2].

Available physiological and pharmacological models that describe the respiratory and cardiopulmonary process are overly complex for use in controller design [3]. To accurately represent individual patients, the (often non-linear) optimization of many parameters is required. Invasive measurements such as blood gas analysis or empirical estimates are often used to reduce the number of model parameters. Therefore, these models are limited in their generic applicability across a diverse set of patients.

Previously, Hahn et al. have applied system identification with an affine transformation to model the end-tidal CO_2 during mechanical ventilation [3]. Pomprapa et al. applied system identification to the end-tidal CO_2 by using a Hammerstein model to approximate the non-linear relationship [4]. We propose using a non-linear grey-box

system identification method, based on a Hammerstein model, to find the patient specific relationship between FiO_2 and SpO_2 .

II. Material and methods

The available data were gathered during animal experiments exploring closed-loop mechanical ventilation. A mechanical ventilator (EVE, Fritz Stephan GmbH, Gackenbach, Germany) ventilated a pig (43 kg) in a pressure-controlled mode. All ventilation data and the oxygen saturation from the integrated sensor were logged at 100 Hz and 1 Hz, respectively, using a real time PC (MicroLabBox, dSPACE GmbH, Paderborn, Germany).

During routine clinical interventions it is not uncommon for clinical staff to briefly set the FiO_2 to 100 % to prevent hypoxemia. Once a patient has stabilized, the FiO_2 is titrated down until the SpO_2 is again within the target region. Our proposed method makes use of such a FiO_2 titration maneuver. Thus, no additional or potentially harmful excitation routines are required. In essence, the input excitation signal (the FiO_2) becomes a downward staircase function.

From previous experience it is known that the relationship of FiO_2 to SpO_2 is clearly non-linear, but that the transient response appears similar in all operating points. For this reason, a system identification using a Hammerstein model is proposed. The model consists of a static non-linear input function and a linear transfer function, $G(s)$, describing the dynamics. These are connected in series as shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1: Block structure of a Hammerstein model.

The model assumes separability of the static non-linearity and the linear dynamics [2].

Given that the input signal is a slow downward staircase function, the identification is split into two processes: a static one, which uses only the stationary points, and a transient process, which considers each step response individually. Using the stationary points, the static input function is approximated by a fourth order polynomial using a non-linear least squares method. For the individual step responses, the input and output are normalized, as the gain is captured in the input function already [2]. Each step response is fit individually by a first order system plus dead time system using the system identification toolbox from MATLAB. The transfer function has unit gain and is given by:

$$G(s) = \frac{1}{\tau \cdot s + 1} \cdot e^{-s \cdot t_d}. \quad (1)$$

Only transfer functions with a goodness of fit of more than 70 % are used. The median of the time constant τ and dead time t_d are then used for the actual model.

III. Results and discussion

The available data included two FiO_2 titrations from one animal experiment: one at the beginning and one at the end. The polynomial fit for the static non-linear function is shown in Fig. 2. From physiology it is known that adapting the positive end-expiratory pressure (PEEP), a further ventilator parameter, will affect the FiO_2 and SpO_2 relationship. This change is clearly visible in Fig. 2. An improved oxygenation (upward shift of the curve) is expected, as PEEP increases the functional residual capacity of the lung, which improves gas exchange.

Figure 2: Static non-linear function approximation of the relationship between FiO_2 and SpO_2 for one animal experiment at two different PEEP levels.

For the linear dynamic transfer function, the time constant τ is 25.41 ± 4.9 sec and the dead time t_d is 22 ± 4.5 sec with a goodness of fit of 84.7 ± 6.7 %. No noticeable difference in the linear dynamics exists between the two titration maneuvers.

As can be seen in Fig. 3, the simulated value follows the measured signal with a good fit. In the time interval between 100 and 120 min the measured SpO_2 signal was extremely noisy due to poor perfusion at the sensor location. Here the model output could be used as a surrogate measurement until the sensor is repositioned.

Figure 3: Result of identification and simulation for one animal experiment.

Despite the above mentioned approach being a grey box approach, the resulting non-linear static curves relating SpO_2 to FiO_2 have some resemblance to the iso-shunt lines proposed by Benatar et al. [5], which were used to estimate the relationship between FiO_2 and arterial partial pressure of oxygen (PaO_2). The PaO_2 can be converted to SpO_2 using the oxygen dissociation equation from [6]. An exemplary iso-shunt line is also shown in Fig. 2.

IV. Conclusions

The patient specific relationship between FiO_2 and SpO_2 can adequately be modelled by a non-linear Hammerstein model. Thereby, physiological closed-loop controller testing can be applied to patient specific simulations. In future, the model can be extended to include further inputs, such as PEEP, to improve the accuracy over a wider range of operating points.

AUTHOR'S STATEMENT

Research funding: This work has been funded by the Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF, Germany) and is part of the project SOLVe with the grant number 13GW0240. Conflict of interest: Authors state no conflict of interest. Informed consent: Not applicable. Ethical approval: In the ongoing in vivo study, all national and European laws, guidelines, and policies for the care and use of laboratory animals are followed.

REFERENCES

- [1] P. von Platen, A. Pomprapa, B. Lachmann, and S. Leonhardt, "The dawn of physiological closed-loop ventilation—a review," *Crit. Care*, vol. 24, no. 1, p. 121, Dec. 2020.
- [2] O. Nelles, *Nonlinear system identification*. 2001.
- [3] Jin-Oh Hahn, G. A. Dumont, and J. M. Ansermino, "System Identification and Closed-Loop Control of End-Tidal CO_2 in Mechanically Ventilated Patients," *IEEE Trans. Inf. Technol. Biomed.*, vol. 16, no. 6, pp. 1176–1184, Nov. 2012.
- [4] A. Pomprapa, B. Misgeld, V. Sorgato, A. Stollenwerk, M. Walter, and S. Leonhardt, "Robust control of end-tidal CO_2 using the Hinf loop shaping approach," *Acta Polytech.*, vol. 53, no. 6, pp. 895–900, Dec. 2013.
- [5] S. R. Benatar, A. M. Hewlett, and J. F. Nunn, "The use of iso-shunt lines for control of oxygen therapy," *Br. J. Anaesth.*, vol. 45, no. 7, pp. 711–718, Jul. 1973.
- [6] J. W. Severinghaus, "Simple, accurate equations for human blood O_2 dissociation computations," *J. Appl. Physiol.*, vol. 46, no. 3, pp. 599–602, Mar. 1979, doi: 10.1152/jappl.1979.46.3.599.